

Kinetics of cationic micelle catalyzed oxidation of cyclohexanone by vanadium(v)

Jagannath Panda and G. P. Panigrahi*

Department of Chemistry, Berhampur University, Berhampur-760 007, India

E-mail : ganesh_panigrahi@yahoo.com

Manuscript received 22 December 2000, revised 16 March 2001, accepted 31 May 2001

Oxidation of cyclohexanone by vanadium(v) in sulfuric acid medium is catalyzed marginally in presence of CTAB and NDPC, reaches a maximum and then decreases. The oxidation rate-[micelle] profile is rationalized by Berezin model and binding constants of both the reactants with the micelle have been computed using the model. The data also fit into Piszkwicz model.

Study on electron transfer reactions in micellar media¹ has assumed importance because electron transport process in biochemical functions² represents reactions of primary importance. Kinetic study of oxidation of cyclohexanone and 2-hydroxycyclohexanone by vanadium(v) in presence of anionic surfactant HClO₄ media has been carried out mainly to understand hydrophobic and electrostatic contributions to micellar effects³. In continuation of the study, the reaction has been investigated in cationic micelles, namely, cetyltrimethylammonium bromide (CTAB) and *N*-dodecylpyridinium chloride (NDPC) and the results are reported in this communication.

Results and Discussion

Littler and Waters⁵ reported the kinetics of oxidation of cyclohexanone in aqueous sulfuric acid medium showing unit dependence in the substrate as well as in [H⁺] at constant ionic strength. The kinetics of the title reaction were investigated in presence of 0.001 M of the surfactant. The dependence in each substrate, H⁺ and salts in presence of constant [CTAB] or [NDPC] remained broadly the same as in the absence of the surfactant. The test for radical formation was found to be positive demonstrating that the reaction proceeds through a radical intermediate. The observed pseudo-first order rate constants are given in Tables. The kinetic data have been used to conclude that cyclohexanone in keto form is attacked by the active form of the V^V species namely [V(OH)₃]²⁺ in slow step.

Reaction in presence of varying [CTAB] : Pseudo-first order rate constants (k_{ψ} , min⁻¹) in presence of varying concentrations of CTAB are presented in Table 1. The data reveal that the reaction is catalyzed marginally and passes through a maximum and then decreases attaining a limiting value.

Table 1. Pseudo-first order rate constants for the oxidation of cyclohexanone by vanadium(v) in presence of CTAB
[V^V] = 0.005 M, [cyclohexanone] = 0.05 M, temp. = 40^o, aqueous solvent

10 ⁴ [CTAB] mol dm ³	10 ³ k _ψ , min ⁻¹		
	[H ₂ SO ₄] = 0.27 M	0.5 M	0.75 M
0.0	1.89	2.86	3.69
2.0	2.28	2.81	4.48
4.0	2.41	4.03	3.50
6.0	2.01	2.72	3.27
8.0	1.98	2.63	3.08
10.0	2.19	2.55	2.94
20.0	1.71	2.41	-
30.0	1.63	2.25	2.82
50.0	1.73	2.22	2.75
70.0	1.47	2.20	2.57
90.0	1.57	2.34	2.51
100.0	1.58	2.13	2.74
120.0	1.47	1.93	2.66
140.0	1.43	2.26	2.61

It is seen that the maximum occurs at a concentration of CTAB which is below the reported CMC (9×10^{-4} M) of CTAB. Appearance of the maximum rate at a [CTAB] below the CMC may be attributed to either submicellar aggregates⁴ are formed or CMC itself is lowered due to presence of added molecules and ions⁶.

In order to rationalize the k_{ψ} - [CTAB] profile, one has to consider both hydrophobic and electrostatic interactions for all the species⁷,

Scheme 1

involved in the reactions, i.e. cyclohexanone as well as the V^V species. Therefore, in the present case, the reaction Scheme 1 applies and the apparent rate constants are given by eq. (1), where $k_m = k_m/V$ (V is a quality related to the volume element for the reaction) and K_s and K_o are the binding constants of the substrate cyclohexanone and the oxidant, i.e. V^V , respectively.

$$k_\psi = \frac{k_w + \bar{k}_m K_o K_s C}{(1 + K_s C)(1 + K_o C)} \quad (1)$$

Assuming $k_w \ll k_m K_o K_s C$, hence k_w can be neglected compared to the second term in the numerator (eq. 1) and on rearranging one can get,

$$\frac{1}{k_\psi} = \frac{1}{k_m K_s K_o C} + \frac{K_s^+ K_o}{k_m K_s K_o} + \frac{C}{\bar{k}_m} \quad (2)$$

According to this equation, the trend of $1/k_\psi$ as function of C would show a minimum and the plot beyond C_{min} would be linear with a positive slope and positive intercept or on the other hand at the optimum⁸ surfactant concentration corresponding to the maximum in the plot a k_ψ against [Surfactant], i.e.

$$C_{opt} = (K_s K_o)^{-1/2}$$

To test the validity of the equations $1/k_\psi$ was plotted against $([C]-CMC)$ values. In fact the plots were linear showing validity of the eq. (1). From the slopes and intercepts of plots, K_o , K_s and \bar{k}_m have been computed (Table 2).

Table 2. Binding constants, transfer free energies of oxidant V^V and substrate cyclohexanone and \bar{k}_m at different $[H_2SO_4]$ in presence of CTAB

Aqueous solvent :					
$[H_2SO_4]$ mol dm ⁻³	$10^5 \bar{k}_m$	$10^{-5} K_s$	K_o	$-\Delta\mu_s^0$ kJ mol ⁻¹	$-\Delta\mu_{ox}^0$ kJ mol ⁻¹
0.27	7.0	2.27	27.47	42.55	19.07
0.50	12.89	6.23	17.83	45.18	17.95
0.75	13.87	11.78	21.23	46.84	18.4

Inspection of the binding constants shows that the parameters for the substrate increase with increase in acid concentration in aqueous medium implying greater binding of the substrate, i.e. cyclohexanone with the micelles of CTAB unlike in sodium lauryl sulfate micelles where no such relationship to acid concentration is observed. Although it is difficult to explain increased binding ability of CTAB to cyclohexanone with increase of $[H^+]$ it may be conjectured that the shape of CTAB micelles may change from spherical shape to rod like structures in presence of higher acid concentration as a result of which the binding constant for the substrate is enormously increased. Change of shape of micellar structure in presence of electrolyte has been recently reported⁴.

Conversely, the binding constant (K_o) of the oxidant with CTAB micelles is very small compared to the K_s values and remains constant at different acid concentra-

tions. Constancy of K_o value suggests that it is bound by hydrophilic forces rather than electrostatic attraction as the active oxidant species as well as the micelle surface are positively charged and hence electrostatic attraction will be a remote possibility. Further variation of $[H^+]$ does not affect the number of hydrophilic sites thus resulting in the constancy of K_o values. Thus one can visualize location of the oxidant species on the Stern layer.

Reaction in presence of [NDPC] : Pseudo-first order constants (k_ψ) measured in presence of the cationic surfactant *N*-dodecylpyridinium chloride (NDPC) are recorded in Table 3. Examination of data shows initial acceleration of rate at lower [NDPC] though moderate, subsequently decreases with increase of surfactant concentration. Plots of the experimental data at three different $[H^+]$ reveal that the rate maximum appears at [NDPC] much below its CMC ($1.5 \times 10^{-2} M$) value as observed in presence of CTAB.

Table 3. Pseudo-first order rate constants for the oxidation of cyclohexanone by vanadium(v) in presence of NDPC at temp. 40°

$[V^V] = 0.005 M$, [cyclohexanone] = 0.05 M, solvent temp. = 40°, aqueous solvent

$10^3 [NDPC]$ mol dm ⁻³	$10^3 k_\psi, \text{min}^{-1}$		
	$[H_2SO_4] = 0.25 M$	$0.5 M$	$0.75 M$
0.0	2.50	3.12	3.74
2.0	2.74	3.25	4.21
4.0	2.30	3.33	4.82
6.0	2.67	3.51	5.61
8.0	2.28	3.07	5.19
10.0	1.87	3.29	4.82
12.0	2.04	2.90	4.54
14.0	1.89	2.86	4.30
16.0	1.74	2.72	4.21
18.0	1.61	2.42	3.56
20.0	1.51	2.58	3.18
24.0	1.55	2.43	3.24
28.0	1.21	2.51	3.04

Plots of $1/k_\psi$ vs [NDPC] are also linear beyond the optimum concentration. However, for this plot, CMC was not subtracted for [NDPC] due to its large magnitude. Scheme 1 and eqs. (1) and (2) are also applicable to the data obtained in presence of varying [NDPC] as in case of CTAB. Using the values of C_{min} , intercepts and slope, binding constant (K_s , K_o) \bar{k}_m values were computed (Table 4). The binding constants of the substrate with the micelle though do not show any trend but are of similar order of magnitude. Similar is the case with the oxidant. However, K_s values are larger than K_o . This suggests that the substrate molecule, namely, cyclohexanone is rather bound to the micellar core by hydrophobic forces and the oxidant to the outer surface by hydrophilic force rather than electrostatic attraction since both the micelle and the oxidant are positively charged.

Table 4. Binding constants, transfer free energies of oxidant V^V and substrate cyclohexanone and \bar{k}_m at different [H₂SO₄] in presence of NDPC

Aqueous solvent :

[H ₂ SO ₄]	10 ⁵ \bar{k}_m	10 ⁻² K _s	10 ⁻² K _o	-Δμ _s ⁰ kJ mol ⁻¹	-Δμ _{ox} ⁰ kJ mol ⁻¹
0.25	4.84	6.63	0.94	27.36	22.28
0.50	18.0	31.01	0.20	31.37	18.27
0.75	14.4	4.93	0.56	26.59	20.94

Transfer free energy values for both the reactants are calculated using the relationship,

$$\Delta\mu^0 = -RT \ln [55.5 K]$$

The Δμ⁰ values are given in Table 4.

To explain the kinetic data in presence of micelles, Piszkiwicz⁹ proposed the following reaction model,

Scheme 2

where K_D is the dissociation constant of the micelle back to its free components, k_m the rate constant with in the micelle and k_w is the rate constant of the reaction not catalyzed by surfactant. The observed rate constant k_ψ as a function of detergent concentration is

$$k_\psi = \frac{k_m[D]^n + k_w K_D}{K_D + [D]^n} \quad (3)$$

The validity of eq. (3) can be established if the plot of log [(k_ψ-k_w)/(k_m-k_ψ)] vs log [D] is linear. However, when the experimental data were fitted to the equation no linearity was observed, establishing inadequacy of the relationship as well as of Scheme 2 for the present reaction. Piszkiwicz¹⁰ consequently proposed the following steps (Scheme 3) to accommodate the decrease of rate constants (k_ψ) at high detergent concentrations :

Scheme 3

In Scheme 3, n' is the additional number of detergent molecules which must associate with catalytic micelle D_nS, to completely inactivate it and K_{n'} is the association constant of this interaction. The above Scheme leads to the kinetic expression (eq. 4),

$$k_\psi = \frac{k_m [D]^n + k_w K_D}{K_D + [D]^n + K_n' [D]^n [D]^{n'}} \quad (4)$$

Eq. (4) changes to eq. (5) at high detergent concentrations,

$$k_\psi = \frac{k_m}{1 + K_n' [D]^{n'}} \quad (5)$$

which may be rearranged to eq.(6),

$$\log [(k_m/k_\psi)-1] = \log K_n' + n' \log [D] \quad (6)$$

Plot of L.H.S. against log [D] if found to be linear with a positive slope, may be taken as a proof of validity of eq. (5) and hence the Scheme.

The experimental data were used to obtain log [(k_m/k_ψ)-1] values which were plotted against the respective log [D] values of both CTAB and NDPC. The plots were found to be linear with a positive slope. The value of n' in all the plots is either fractional or close to one although Piszkiwicz predicted a value between 3 and 1. The magnitude of n' in the present study suggests that probably a small fraction of the surfactants are involved in forming inhibiting catalysts and the intercepts of the plots equal to log K_{n'} have a negative sign. This means K_{n'} values are again very small which rules out formation of inhibitory catalysts in appreciable amounts. Nonetheless Piszkiwicz model has been partially successful to explain the decrease of rate in presence of higher surfactant concentrations. On the other hand, the decrease of rate in presence of large concentration of the surfactant can be attributed to dilution of the reactants in the micellar medium.

Experimental

All the reagents used were of A.R. grade. Stock solutions of V^V were prepared in double-distilled water by dissolving appropriate amount of ammonium vanadate and sulfuric acid. Stock solutions of CTAB and NDPC were prepared in double-distilled water. Reactant solution of cyclohexanone was prepared. Appropriate amount of stock surfactant solution was added to the oxidant and made up. V^V solution was standardized by redox titration¹¹. Reaction was started by mixing 50 ml of each of the thermally equilibrated reactants in a stoppered bottle placed in a thermostat and kinetics of oxidation were followed by monitoring the residual V^V at different time intervals. The surfactants were stable throughout the period of the kinetic run. Results were reproducible within the limits of experimental error.

References

1. C. Minero, E. Pramauro, E. Pelizzetti and D. Meissel, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1983, **87**, 399; F. P. Cavalino, C. Sbriziolo and E. Pelizzetti, *Ber. Bunsenges. Phys. Chem.*, 1983, **87**, 843; F. Sanchez, M. L. Moya, A. Rodriguez, R. Jimenez, C. Gomez-Herrera, C. Yanes and P. Lopez-Cornejo, *Langmuir*, 1997, **13**, 3084; F. Sanchez, M. L. Moya, R. Jimenez, C. Gomez-Herrera, M. C. Carmona and P. Lopez-Cornejo, *J. Chem. Soc., Faraday Trans.*, 1997, **93**, 2181; M. Davies and S. J. Foggo, *J. Chem. Soc., Perkin Trans. 2*, 1998, 247; M. S. Krishnamachari, K. Ramakrishna, C. Somyajula, P. Syamala and P. V. S. Rao, *J. Mol. Catl., A : Chem.*, 1997, **123**, 103; P. V. S. Rao, G. K. Rao, K. Ramakrishna, G. Rambabu and A. Satyanarayana, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1996, **35**, 969.
2. N. Sutin in "Inorganic Biochemistry", ed. G. I. Eichhorn, Elsevier,

Panda *et al.* : Kinetics of cationic micelle catalyzed oxidation of cyclohexanone by vanadium(V)

- Amsterdam, 1973, Vol. 2, Chap. 19; S. Wheland and H. B. Gray in "Biological Aspects of Inorganic Biochemistry", ed. A. W. Addison. Wiley, New York, 1977, Chap. 10.
3. G. P. Panigrahi and R. Swain, *J. Surf. Sci. Technol.*, communicated.
 4. M. van der Auweraer and F. C. De Schryver, *Chem. Phys.*, 1987, **111**, 105.
 5. J. S. Littler and W. A. Waters, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, 3014.
 6. C. A. Bunton in "Surfactants in Solution", eds. K. L. Mittal and D. O. Shah, Plenum, New York, Vol. II.
 7. E. Perez-Benito and E. Rodenas, *Langmuir*, 1991, **7**, 232, and references cited therein; A. I. Carbone, F. P. Cavasino, E. Di Dio and C. Sbriziolo *Int. J. Chem. Kinet.*, 1968, **18**, 609.
 8. I. V. Berezin, K. Martinek and A. K. Yatsimirskii. *Russ. Chem. Rev. (Eng. Transl.)*, 1973, **42**, 787.
 9. Ref. 8, p. 794.
 10. D. Piskiewicz, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1976, **98**, 3053; 1977, **99**, 1550, 7695.
 11. A. I. Vogel, "Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", ELBS, London, 1971.